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Development of a Decision Support System for increasing the resilience of urban road network

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A blue-tinted background image of a city street map, showing a grid of roads and a central water body.

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A blue-tinted aerial photograph of a complex highway interchange with multiple overpasses and ramps. A large white number '1' is overlaid on the image.

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Introduction and Task

Assumption

- Climate changing
- Increased hurricanes, floods, fires, tornadoes and earthquakes
- Floods are the climatic factors causing the most significant impacts on transport infrastructure

Methodology

Event Analysis

Underground Analysis

Hydraulic Analysis

Microsimulation Model

Emergency Plan

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Event and Reference Analysis

Event Analysis

Hydraulic Analysis

Accessibility Map

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Underground Analysis

Underground Analysis

Video Cameras

Web- Application

Traffic Light

Short-Term Activities

Medium Term Activities

Study Area 1

Study Area 2

Study Area 3

Medium Term Activities

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Microsimulation Model

Microsimulation Model

Microscopic simulation models simulate the movement of individual vehicles based on car-following and lane-changing theories

INPUT

Geometric Data

- Number of lanes; Lane width; Link length; Bus stop locations; Crosswalks; etc...

Traffic Control Data

- Traffic lights cycle; Yield; Stop; etc...

Traffic Demand

- Traffic flow by vehicle type; Turn ratio on the junctions; O-D/path-specific and vehicle data; PT operations; Bicycle and pedestrian demand data.

Driver Behavior

- Driver's aggressiveness (Acceleration, deceleration, reaction time); Driver's response to information (Vehicle Message Signal)

OUTPUT

- Level of Service (LOS)
- Delay
- Speed
- Travel Time
- Volume
- Queue Length
- Number of Stops
- Average Vehicle Occupancy (AVO)
- Volume-to-Capacity (V/C)
- Density

Microsimulation Model

Tommaso Natale – Exit Ramp

Via Belgio – Exit Ramp

Microsimulation Model

Via Nicoletti Roundabout

Via Belgio Junction

Via Nebrodi Junction

Scenarios

Reference Scenario

- Reference scenario
- Time: 16:00 – 17:00
- Average flow

Emergency Scenario

- Scenario considering the *Tommaso Natale* and *Via Belgio* Emergency Plan
- Time: 16:00 – 17:00
- Traffic diversion from Viale Regione Siciliana:
 - 100% Truck and 20% car to Nicoletti Roundabout.
 - 60% car to Belgio Junction
 - 20% car to Nebrodi Junction

Results - LOS

Via Nicoletti Roundabout

Reference

Emergency

Results - LOS

Via Belgio Junction

Reference

Emergency

Results - LOS

Via Nebrodi Junction

Reference

Emergency

A blue-tinted aerial photograph of a complex highway interchange with multiple overpasses and ramps. The image is semi-transparent, allowing the text to be overlaid.

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Discussion and Conclusion

Discussion

- The world **climate change** and the return time of this event could be different.
- The development of trip **demand matrices** is crucial for any form of modelling
- Using a simulation model can provide the effects generated by different scenarios built under various "**what if?**". This can lead to the elaboration of specific plans when a maintenance project is drawn up, which involves a temporary reduction in the capacity of the arcs/nodes of the network involved in the emergency
- Sudden disruptions along the major road network can lead to significant traffic congestion and a large increase in average vehicle journey times, particularly if the proportion of **HGVs** during the evacuation is relatively high.
- Although the network in our case study is topologically simple, the method could be applied to a **more complex network** that may exhibit non-linear effects in evacuation travel times due to the regulation of intersections and queues limiting turns.

Extend the Area Analysis of the Microsimulation Model considering all underpasses.

Further Analysis

In Short-Term:

- Add a new Scenario in the Microsimulation Model to **optimise the traffic light system** in the junctions via Belgio and Via dei Nebrodi

In Medium-Term:

- Impact Study of using **automatic traffic counting systems** (cameras and big data) to estimate traffic flows along the network
- Impact Study of **ITS systems** to improve user information
- Calculate a new theoretical **return period** for this flood

 Thank you!